

Potential Antibacterial Use of Selected Seaweed Species Against Aquaculture Pathogens

Donica O. Lorenzo¹, Jeffrey F. Usigan¹, R Jay M. Tuppil¹, Emma L. Ballard, PhD² and Glycinea M. De Peralta¹

¹Cagayan State University – Aparri Campus, Maura, Aparri, Cagayan, Philippines

²Department of Agriculture - Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (DA-BFAR) Region 2, Tuguegarao City, Cagayan, Philippines

Corresponding Author: Emma L. Ballard ✉ elballad@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Pathogens in the aquaculture industry have threatened commercially important fish species, leading to significant losses, and conventional drugs used to combat these pathogens are usually expensive. Plants are good medicinal alternatives as they contain bioactive compounds. Seaweeds *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* are abundant at the intertidal zones of Nangaramoan Beach in Sta. Ana, Cagayan, Philippines and have shown potential inhibitory properties against pathogenic bacteria. Despite their abundance, these remain understudied. This study aimed 1) to evaluate the presence of bioactive compounds in the methanolic and ethanolic extracts from *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.*, and 2) to assess their effectiveness in inhibiting the growth of selected pathogens at various concentrations: 1.0 mg/mL, 0.75 mg/mL, and 0.5 mg/mL. The phytochemical screening of *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* utilized qualitative test tube screening methods. The methanolic and ethanolic extracts of both seaweeds were subjected to the paper disc agar diffusion method against two aquaculture pathogens, namely *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, to assess the antibacterial activities with Amoxicillin (Benedex) and distilled water as the positive and negative controls, respectively. The phytochemical analysis revealed that *Ulva spp.* methanolic extract contains flavonoids, while its ethanolic extract contains flavonoids and tannins similar to *Padina spp.* methanolic extract. The ethanolic extract of *Padina spp.* contains all three bioactive compounds: flavonoids, saponins, and tannins. In addition, the antimicrobial screening revealed that *S. aureus* is the most susceptible pathogen to both extracts due to factors, such as bacteria type and dosage dependency. While the results showed that inhibitory activity is significantly lower than the positive control ($p > 0.05$), the study revealed that *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* have promising antibacterial properties. These extracts are, therefore, recommended to be tested against other aquaculture pathogens and further explored for possible drug formulation.

Keywords: Bioactive Compounds, Phytochemical Analysis, Paper Disc Diffusion Method, Zone of Inhibition, Antimicrobial Screening

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture has experienced rapid growth and is recognized as a primary means of increasing food production in the future (Troell et al., 2013). However, this sector faces challenges caused by various pathogens, leading to bacterial diseases that pose health threats to commercially important fish species and result in significant economic losses (Pridgeon and Klesius, 2013; Roh et al., 2016). The majority of the drugs employed to combat these pathogens are costly. In addition, pathogens evolve to resist antimicrobials like antibiotics, antivirals, and antifungals, posing a crucial challenge to modern medicine (Yilmaz and Schiffer, 2021). According to Pepi and Focardi (2021), using antibiotics in aquaculture induced antibiotic resistance in the surrounding bacteria in the column water, sediment, and fish-associated bacterial strains. With this, there is a need to explore and develop cheaper and more effective natural antimicrobial agents with better potential, fewer side effects than antibiotics, good bioavailability, and minimal toxicity (Thanigaivel, 2015; Perez et al., 2016).

Numerous studies highlight the potential of plants not only as sources of sustenance but also as sources of chemical compounds found in specific plant parts, which can be utilized as medicines for treating various diseases (Sofowora et al., 2013). According to Saidin et al. (2021), both inorganic and organic antibacterial agents demonstrated identical trends in suppressing both gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria; however, their antibacterial effectiveness is also dependent on the species of bacterial strain and respective mechanism owned by each antibacterial agent. In the Philippines, using plant-based traditional medicines remains widespread, attributed to the cost-effectiveness of preparing plant-based remedies, its proven efficacy, and the minimal complications associated with its use in treating common ailments.

Seaweeds are macrobenthic marine algae known as prominent components of shallow marine producers (Trono, 1997). These are utilized in several industrial

products as raw materials, such as agar, algin, and carrageenan, but are still widely consumed as food in several nations (Vieira et al., 2018). In addition, seaweed showcases antibacterial activities and

can function as antioxidants, attributed to the bioactive compounds generated through secondary metabolism. However, the presence of these compounds may vary depending on the season (Adegbaaju et al., 2020), environmental factors (Sivagnanam et al., 2015), and extraction solvent (Sobuj et al., 2021).

Green seaweeds, according to Lakshmi et al. (2020), are cheap sources of predominant biomaterials and high-value chemicals, such as polyunsaturated fatty acids, carotenoids, phycobilins, and polysaccharides. For instance, HarshaMohan et al. (2023) stated in their study that *Ulva*, a green seaweed species, is a good source of vitamins B, proteins, minerals like calcium, potassium, magnesium, sodium, copper, iron, and iodine, as well as dietary fibers and carotenoids. *Ulva* species are among the most abundant representatives in coastal benthic communities worldwide; however, the genus as a whole has been relatively underexplored (Wichard et al., 2015), with a lack of research on *Ulva* species, such as *U. fasciata* and *U. reticulata*. Aside from the green seaweeds, Ayrapetyan et al. (2021) noted in their study that brown seaweeds are also known to contain bioactive compounds, including sulfated polysaccharides (fucoindans), which are considered promising antimicrobial components for various applications in medicine and the food industry. The study of Rachmawati et al. (2021) found that *P. australis* contains alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and antioxidants. Still, *Padina sp.* is one of the understudied brown seaweeds (Hanry et al., 2022).

The abundance of *Ulva* and *Padina* along the intertidal zone of Nangaramoan Beach, San Vicente, Sta. Ana Cagayan has been identified in the study of Baleta and Nalleb (2016). This study aimed 1) to evaluate the presence of bioactive compounds in the methanolic and ethanolic extracts from *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* collected

from August to September, and 2) to assess their effectiveness in inhibiting the growth of selected pathogens at various concentrations: 1.0 mg/mL, 0.75 mg/mL, and 0.5 mg/mL.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The seaweed samples (*Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.*) were collected from the intertidal zones of Nangaramoan Beach, San Vicente, Sta. Ana, Cagayan, during August to September. The seaweed maceration and methanolic and ethanolic crude extracts extraction were conducted at the Department of Agriculture - Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources Regional Office 2 - Fisheries Integrated Laboratory Section in Tuguegarao City, Cagayan. The bacteria (*Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) were acquired from Saint Paul University Philippines Science Laboratory, Tuguegarao City, Cagayan, where the antimicrobial screening was also conducted. Finally, the phytochemical analysis was

performed at the Department of Science and Technology Regional Standards and Testing Laboratory (DOST-RSTL), Carig Sur, Tuguegarao, Cagayan. The experimental flow process is shown in Figure 1. Samples of *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* were collected from the field. These were washed and left to be air-dried for a week and were pulverized for the maceration process. The solutions were filtered and concentrated through the vacuum-pressured rotary evaporator to obtain the crude extracts used for the phytochemical and antimicrobial analysis.

Phytochemical Analysis

About 50 mL of *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* methanolic and ethanolic extract were brought to the DOST RO2-RSTL for the phytochemical screening (Guevarra et al., 2005).

Figure 1. Research Methodological Flow.

Preparation of the different concentrations

For the 0.75 mg/L concentration, 2.25 mL of the crude extract was mixed with 0.75 mL of distilled water, while 1.5 mL of the crude extract was mixed with 1.5 mL of distilled water for the .50 mg/L concentration. These dilution procedures were applied individually for each crude extract, resulting in twelve (12) vials.

Antimicrobial Screening

The paper disk agar diffusion method was used to determine the antimicrobial properties of the sample. 3 mL of each ethanolic and methanolic crude extract in different concentrations (assay solution), distilled water (negative control), and amoxicillin (positive control) were dispensed into the sterile paper discs and were performed in five (5) replicates per seaweed species. The impregnated discs were aseptically applied and pressed into the seeded nutrient agar equidistantly. The assay plates were arranged inside the biosafety cabinet. The petri dishes were incubated at 35°C for 20 hours.

After 20 hours of incubation, the diameters of the zones of inhibition (ZOI) were measured in millimeters using a Vernier caliper and with a black paper background. Clear and well-defined ZOI around the discs are observed if the sample tested possessed antibacterial potential, and the failure of the disc to exhibit zones of inhibition indicates the absence of antibacterial effects.

Statistical Analysis

Mean values \pm SD were used to present the antibacterial efficacy of the *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* extracts against selected aquaculture pathogens based on the average measurement of the ZOI, which were expressed in millimeters using a Vernier caliper. The data were initially tested for normality and homogeneity of variance using Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests, respectively. Parametric data were analyzed using Oneway ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD Test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The seaweed samples used in the study were identified with the assistance of the DA-Bureau of Fisheries and

Aquatic Resources Regional Office 2 based on their morphological characteristics. Two species of *Ulva* were identified as *U. reticulata* and *U. fasciata*, and three species of *Padina* were identified as *P. minor*, *P. australis*, and *P. japonica*.

Table 1. Result of the Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis.

Seaweed Species	Sample Description	Parameter	Result
<i>Ulva spp.</i>	Methanolic crude extract	Flavonoids	+
		Tannins	-
		Saponins	-
	Ethanolic crude extract	Flavonoids	+
		Tannins	+
		Saponins	-
<i>Padina spp.</i>	Methanolic crude extract	Flavonoids	+
		Tannins	+
		Saponins	-
	Ethanolic crude extract	Flavonoids	+
		Tannins	+
		Saponins	+

Table 1 shows the results of the phytochemical analysis and reveals that *Ulva spp.* methanolic extract contains flavonoids.

Both *Ulva spp.* ethanolic extract and *Padina spp.* methanolic extract contain flavonoids and tannins. The ethanolic extract of *Padina spp.* contains all three bioactive compounds: flavonoids, tannins, and saponins. The phytochemical analysis was limited to qualitative contents only due to reagent limitations.

Table 2 indicates the mean and standard deviation (mean \pm SD) of the ZOI (mm) of *Ulva spp.* extracts in different concentrations (1.0 mg/mL, 0.75 mg/mL, and 0.5 mg/mL) tested on *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, wherein the 1.0 mg/mL concentration of both *Ulva spp.* crude extracts exhibited very active inhibition against *S. aureus* (methanolic crude extract 20.68 ± 0.975064 and ethanolic crude extract with 25.47 ± 0.92). The 0.75 mg/mL ethanolic crude extract of *Ulva spp.* exhibited active inhibition with 18.87 ± 1.12 , and 0.5 mg/mL exhibited partially active inhibition with 13.24 ± 1.05 . On the other hand, all the other crude extracts (*Ulva spp.* methanolic and ethanolic crude extract in all concentrations against *E. coli* and

methanolic extract at 0.75 mg/mL and 0.50 mg/mL against *S. aureus*) exhibited inactive inhibition against the selected pathogens.

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation (mean \pm SD) of the ZOI of *Ulva spp.* extracts at different concentrations against selected aquaculture pathogenic bacteria.

Extracts and Concentration		Zone of Inhibition (mm)	
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
<i>Ulva spp.</i> ethanolic crude extract	1.0 mg/mL	6.4 \pm 0.42	25.47 \pm 0.92
	0.75 mg/mL	6.09 \pm 0.12	18.87 \pm 1.12
	0.5 mg/mL	6.00 \pm 0	13.24 \pm 1.05
	Positive Control	18.79 \pm 1.13	28.99 \pm 1.92
	Negative Control	---	---
<i>Ulva spp.</i> methanolic crude extract	1.0 mg/mL	6.71 \pm 0.5	20.68 \pm 0.98
	0.75 mg/mL	6.12 \pm 0.27	8.00 \pm 1.45
	0.5 mg/mL	6.00 \pm 0	7.16 \pm 1.10
	Positive Control	19.1 \pm 1.42	30.26 \pm 1.75
	Negative Control	---	---

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation (mean \pm SD) of the ZOI of *Padina spp.* extracts at different concentrations against selected aquaculture pathogenic bacteria.

Extracts and Concentration		Zone of Inhibition (mm)	
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
<i>Padina spp.</i> ethanolic crude extract	1.0 mg/mL	10.70 \pm 0.64	20.65 \pm 1.40
	0.75 mg/mL	8.00 \pm 0.85	17.42 \pm 0.63
	0.5 mg/mL	6.22 \pm 0.38	8.17 \pm 0.58
	Positive Control	18.08 \pm 1.46	31.73 \pm 1.10
	Negative Control	---	---
<i>Padina spp.</i> methanolic crude extract	1.0 mg/mL	18.41 \pm 1.18	19.80 \pm 1.13
	0.75 mg/mL	13.98 \pm 0.55	15.05 \pm 0.21
	0.5 mg/mL	10.43 \pm 0.55	11.05 \pm 0.07
	Positive Control	21.38 \pm 0.68	30.55 \pm 0.64
	Negative Control	---	---

Table 3 indicates the mean and standard deviation (mean \pm SD) of the ZOI (mm) of *Padina spp.* extracts in different concentrations (1.0 mg/mL, 0.75 mg/mL, and 0.5 mg/mL) against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. It shows that *S. aureus* is more susceptible to both the extracts of *Padina spp.* at 1.0 mg/mL compared to *E. coli* with 20.65 \pm 1.40 (ethanolic crude extract) and 19.80 \pm 1.13 (methanolic crude extract), exhibiting very active inhibition. Meanwhile, the 1.0 mg/mL methanolic crude extract against *E. coli* exhibited active inhibition with 18.41 \pm 1.18, and 1.0 mg/mL ethanolic crude extract exhibited

partially active inhibition with 10.70 \pm 0.64. The 0.75 mg/mL of the methanolic and ethanolic crude extracts also exhibited active inhibition against *S. aureus* with 15.05 mm \pm 0.21 and 17.42 \pm 0.63, respectively. On the other hand, the crude extracts at 0.75 mg/mL concentrations against *E. coli* exhibited partially active inhibition with 13.98 \pm 0.55 (methanolic) and inactive inhibition with 8 \pm 0.85 (ethanolic). The 0.5 mg/mL methanolic crude extract exhibited partially active inhibition against *E. coli* with 10.43 \pm 0.55 and against *S. aureus* with 11.05 \pm 0.07. Finally, the 0.5 mg/mL ethanolic crude extract against both pathogens exhibited inactive inhibition.

Phytochemical Analysis

In the present study, *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* methanolic and ethanolic crude extracts were subjected to a qualitative analysis for the occurrence of three phytochemicals: flavonoids, saponins, and tannins. The test was only limited to qualitative analysis; no quantification was made due to limitations of available reagents.

The results of the phytochemical analysis revealed that *Ulva spp.* methanolic extract contains flavonoids. In the studies of Xie et al. (2014) and Górnaiak et al. (2019), flavonoids have been found to lower adhesion and biofilm formation, porin on the cell membrane, membrane permeability, and pathogenicity, which are considered crucial for the growth of bacteria. The current study also revealed that the ethanolic extracts of *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* contain both flavonoids and tannins. As cited in the study of Kaczmarek (2020), tannins are bioactive compounds that interfere with cell metabolism and cause its destruction once these pass through the bacterial cell wall up to the internal membrane. In the current study, the third bioactive compound, saponins, was only present in the ethanolic extract of *Padina spp.* According to Arabski et al. (2012) and Khan et al. (2018), saponins may enhance the permeability of bacterial membranes, potentially facilitating the influx of

antibiotics through the bacterial cell wall membrane. However, the presence of phytoconstituents is mostly determined by numerous factors such as seasonal variations (Adegbaju et al., 2020) and environmental factors (Sivagnanam et al. 2015), as well as the extraction solvents used for brown and green seaweeds (Sobuj et al., 2021). According to Adegbaju et al. (2020), the levels of plant phenolic compounds are affected and significantly altered by seasonal variations in photoperiod, light intensity, and temperature. The collection of the samples was conducted during the rainy months of August to September along the intertidal zones of Nangaramoan beach. Zhang et al. (2020) revealed in their study that total phenolic content is significantly higher during the wet season than during the rest of the year.

Another factor that could affect the presence of extracted bioactive compounds is the solvent used (Sobuj et al., 2021). The current study utilized methanol and ethanol as extraction solvents. According to Prasetyaningrum et al. (2021), solvent ethanol can get the flavonoid content due to its polar side. This supports the current study, which revealed that ethanol was more effective in yielding bioactive compounds than methanol, where ethanol extracted 5 of the 6 bioactive compounds while methanol only extracted 3. In addition, the current study aligns with the study of Nawaz et al. (2020), wherein extraction in highly polar solvents, like methanol, leads to low phenolic (including tannins) and flavonoid content compared to non-polar solvents. *Ulva spp.* ethanolic crude extract in the present study contains both flavonoids and tannins, whereas its methanolic crude extract only contains flavonoids. The study of Anis et al. (2018) further supports this, revealing that the methanolic extract of *U. fasciata* contains flavonoids but at a low concentration of 0.0313%.

The type of seaweed used can affect the presence of phytoconstituents. The current study revealed that the methanolic crude extract of *Padina spp.* exhibited a higher number of bioactive compounds compared to the methanolic extract of *Ulva spp.* According to Nallamuthu

(2013), methanol is particularly suitable for extracting antimicrobials from brown seaweeds. The present study also indicates that the ethanolic crude extract of *Padina spp.* contains all 3 bioactive compounds. This is supported by the study of Rachmawati et al. (2021) on *P. australis*, wherein the presence of saponins, tannins, and flavonoids was noted. On the other hand, the methanolic crude extract of *Padina spp.* in the current study includes flavonoids and tannins but lacks saponins. This finding aligns with the results of Khadijah et al. (2021), where the methanol extract of *Padina sp.* contains flavonoids and tannins but lacks saponins.

Numerous studies have explored chemical compounds derived from macroalgae, revealing a spectrum of biological activities dependent upon variables such as the specific algae and microorganisms involved (Centeno and Ballantine, 1999; Pooja, 2014). In the study of Remya et al. (2022), brown algae contain bioactive compounds, such as phlorotannin, fucoxanthin, alginic acid, fucoidan, and laminarin, while *U. reticulata* (green algae) in the study of Julyasih and Purnawati (2023) revealed that terpenoid, phenolic, and alkaloid are the phytochemical compounds present. Moreover, the phytochemical screening in the study of Singkoh et al. (2021) revealed that the ethanolic extracts of brown algae *P. australis* contained flavonoids, saponins, and tannins and could inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. mutans*, and *Escherichia coli*.

Antibacterial Assay

Algal compounds have been proven to be good sources of bioactive compounds with many potentialities. Numerous studies confirmed that the seaweeds chemical composition and antimicrobial activity vary with geographic location, ecological factors, collection time, and physiological conditions (Pérez et al., 2016). Moreover, Pérez et al. (2016) noted that a lack of antibacterial activity was reported during some seasons. *Phaeophyceae* showed inactivity in certain seasons, while *Chlorophyceae* were active throughout the year. In the current study, brown seaweed *Padina spp.* showed high

antibacterial activity against the pathogenic bacteria tested, while the green seaweed *Ulva spp.* exhibited high antibacterial activity only to *S. aureus*.

Due to the different content of bioactive compounds as proven in the phytochemical screening, the crude extracts of *Padina spp.* and *Ulva spp.* exhibited significantly different inhibitory activity against the fish pathogenic bacteria tested.

Both the ethanolic and methanolic extracts of *Padina spp.* produced consistent active ZOI against the two pathogenic bacteria, while the extracts of *Ulva spp.* exhibited active inhibitory activity against *S. aureus* only, but not against *E. coli*. Similar observations were recorded in the study of Srikong et al. (2017), wherein the algal extracts of *Padina sp.* showed no antibacterial activity against gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella enteric* but showed inhibitory activity against gram-positive bacteria strains (*S. aureus*), which could be due to the differences in the capability of the extraction protocols to recover any inhibitory phytochemicals and different assay methods, resulting in the different susceptibilities of target bacteria strains.

In the current study, higher inhibition activity yielded by extracts of the brown seaweeds compared to the green seaweeds also suggests that the antibacterial activity depends on the class of seaweed. These findings are similar to the observations of Oumaskour et al. (2012), where several species showing active inhibition against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria were recorded in the class of *Phaeophyceae* rather than *Chlorophyceae*.

In addition to this, the results of the study also showed the differences in the ZOI of the extracts. The methanolic extract of *Ulva spp.* showed the lowest inhibition compared to the other extracts was due to the extract containing only one single phytochemical constituent (flavonoids), as compared to the other extracts with two

and three bioactive compounds. According to Monteiro et al. (2019), solvent choice is another determinant in the yield of antioxidant activities of algal extracts due to the solvent influence in the solubilization of antioxidant compounds. The results of the current study align with the observation recorded in the study of Nisha et al. (2014), wherein methanol extracts of red and green seaweeds had significantly lower antimicrobial activity than brown seaweed. Pérez et al. (2016) suggested using acetone, while Nisha et al. (2014) suggested using 50:50 ethanol and water, or 50:50 methanol and water for extraction of green seaweed species.

The result of the current study also showed that the inhibitory properties of the seaweed extracts were dose-dependent. Higher concentrations of the different algal extracts exhibited higher inhibitory activities and decreased as the concentration of the seaweed extracts became lower. The same trends in the results were reported in the studies of Vatsos and Rebours (2015) and Gupta et al. (2012). Both the methanolic and ethanolic extracts of *Padina spp.* and *Ulva spp.* were found active for all microorganisms tested down to 0.50 mg/mL dilution. However, both extracts of *Padina spp.* showed higher ZOI for *S. aureus* compared to *E. coli*.

The effectiveness of the bioactive compounds is also dependent on the type of organisms. In general, gram-positive bacteria were reported to be more vulnerable to algal extracts than gram-negative bacteria due to the differences in their cell structure and composition (Ali et al., 2020). Gram-positive bacteria were marked by dense peptidoglycan in the outer layer of their cell wall, while gram-negative bacteria have composite, multilayered cell wall structures that make the entry of bioactive compounds more difficult (Arguelles and Sapin, 2020); thus, gram-negative bacteria have higher resistance to antibiotics than gram-positive bacteria (Breijayeh, 2020). In the current study, the extracts showed higher inhibition against the gram-positive bacteria, *S. aureus* than to the gram-negative bacteria, *E. coli*; however, the

seaweed extracts showed inhibitory activity against both fish pathogenic bacteria tested lower than the positive control.

In the view of the present study, the knowledge of the inhibitory activity of the methanolic and ethanolic crude extracts from *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* suggests that these extracts can be utilized as promising sources of antibacterial substances. This also suggests their potential application in aquaculture, particularly in addressing diseases in fish caused by *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Nevertheless, these extracts should be tested against other aquaculture pathogens to comprehensively evaluate their efficacy.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the findings of the study, the methanolic and ethanolic extracts derived from *Padina spp.* and *Ulva spp.* collected along the intertidal zones of Nangaramoan Beach, Sta. Ana, Cagayan, Philippines during August to September, possess inhibitory effects against selected aquaculture pathogens: *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. These effects are attributed to the phytochemical constituents present, which are known for their antibacterial properties. These bioactive compounds are flavonoids, tannins, and saponins. The current study revealed that *Ulva spp.* methanolic extract contains flavonoids, and *Ulva spp.* ethanolic extract contains flavonoids and tannins similar *Padina spp.* methanolic extract *Padina spp.* ethanolic extract contains all three bioactive compounds: flavonoids, saponins, and tannins. The study also found that *S. aureus* demonstrated the highest susceptibility to all extracts compared to *E. coli*. Specifically, both methanolic and ethanolic crude extracts of *Padina spp.* and the ethanolic extract of *Ulva spp.* exhibited partially active inhibition at 0.5 mg/mL against *S. aureus*. However, the methanolic extract of *Ulva spp.* showed inactive inhibition at 0.75 mg/mL against *S. aureus*. The crude extracts of *Ulva spp.* and the methanolic extract of *Padina spp.* demonstrated inactive inhibition at 1.0 mg/mL, and the methanolic extract of *Padina spp.* showed partially active inhibition at

0.75 mg/mL against *E. coli*. Finally, the study revealed that inhibitory activity is significantly lower than the positive control. Nevertheless, the study implies that the seaweeds *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* hold promise for potential exploration and development for both preventive and therapeutic purposes due to their antibacterial attributes, and seaweeds could serve as viable alternatives in developing new drugs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers would like to state some recommendations for the institution and other interested researchers. Based on aforementioned findings, the following recommendations are drawn:

1. The use of other extraction methods, solvents, and analysis techniques to identify and quantify the phytochemical constituents, including their antibacterial properties, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* chemical compositions.
2. Conduct tests on other seaweeds species, especially those commercially cultured for ease in sample collection, to evaluate their potential inhibitory effects against other aquaculture pathogens (i.e., *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *A. salmonicida*, *salmonicida*, *Streptococcus spp.*, *Vibrio spp.*, etc.).
3. Conduct of additional research on antimicrobial susceptibility methods or confirmatory tests should identify the antibacterial effectiveness of *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* extracts.
4. Further studies should be undertaken using specific *Ulva* and *Padina* species taken during the other months. This is to identify which species has the most inhibitory properties or the potential to serve as an antibacterial agent. Additionally, it aims to determine which month exhibits the highest concentration of bioactive compounds.
5. Exploration of bioactive compounds present in seaweeds. The government and the academic community are urged to promote and fund research

on bioactive compounds in seaweeds to develop new drugs and address antibiotic resistance.

6. Raise awareness in promoting the sustainable utilization and harvesting of *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.* The government and relevant departments should launch programs to raise awareness and enhance understanding of the utilization of *Ulva spp.* and *Padina spp.*, especially in regions where these resources are abundant.

REFERENCES

- Adegbaju, O. D., Otunola, G. A., and Afolayan, A. J. (2020).** Effects of growth stage and seasons on the phytochemical content and antioxidant activities of crude extracts of *Celosia argentea* L. *Heliyon*, 6(6), 11 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04086>
- Ali, A. H., Moustafa, E. E., Abdelkader, S. A., Hafez, S. S., and Abdallah, S. A. (2020).** Antibacterial potential of macro and microalgae extracts against pathogens relevant to human health. *Plant Archives*, 20(2), 9629-9642.
- Altemimi, A., Lakhssassi, N., Baharlouei, A., Watson, D. G., and Lightfoot, D. A. (2017).** Phytochemicals: Extraction, Isolation, and Identification of Bioactive Compounds from Plant Extracts. *Plants (Basel, Switzerland)*, 6(4), 42. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants6040042>
- Arabski, M., Węgierek-Ciuk, A., Czerwonka, G., Lankoff, A., and Kaca, W. (2012).** Effects of Saponins against Clinical *E. coli* Strains and Eukaryotic Cell Line. *Journal of Biomedicine and Biotechnology*, 2012, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/2862>
- 16 Arguelles, E. D. L. R. and Sapin, A. B. (2020).** Bioactive properties of *Sargassum siliquosum* J. Agardh (Fucales, Ochrophyta) and its potential as a source of skin-lightening active ingredient for cosmetic application. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 10(7), 051-058.
- Ayrapetyan, O. N., Obluchinskaya, E. D., Zhurishkina, E. V., Skorik, Y. A., Lebedev, D. V., Kulminskaya, A. A., and Lapina, I. M. (2021).** Antibacterial Properties of Fucoidans from the Brown Algae *Fucus vesiculosus* L. of the Barents Sea. *Biology*, 10(1), 67. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology10010067>
- Baleta, F. N. and Nalleb, J. P. (2016).** Species composition, abundance, and diversity of seaweeds along the intertidal zone of Nangaramoan, San Vicente Sta. Ana, Cagayan, Philippines. *AAFL Bioflux* 9(2), 250- 259.
- Boy, H. I. A., Rutilla, A. J. H., Santos, K. A., Ty, A. M. T., Yu, A. I., Mahboob, T., Tangpoong, J., and Nissapatorn, V. (2018).** Recommended Medicinal Plants as Source of Natural Products: A Review. *Digital Chinese Medicine*, 1(2), 131-142. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2589-3777\(19\)30018-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2589-3777(19)30018-7)
- Breijyeh, Z., Jubeh, B., and Karaman, R. (2020).** Resistance of Gram-Negative Bacteria to Current Antibacterial Agents and Approaches to Resolve It. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 25(6), 1340. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25061340>
- Cagalj, M., Skroza, D., Tabanelli, G., Ozogul, F., and Simat, V., (2021).** Maximizing the antioxidant capacity of *Padina pavonica* by choosing the right drying and extraction methods. *Processes*, 9(4), 587. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9040587>
- Centeno, P.O.R. and Ballantine, D.L. (1999).** Effects of culture conditions on production of antibioticly active metabolites by the marine alga *Spyridia filamentosa* (Ceramiaceae, Rhodophyta). I. Light. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 11, 217-224 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008113108834>

- Choudhary, B., Chauhan, O. P., and Mishra, A. (2021).** Edible Seaweeds: A Potential Novel Source of Bioactive Metabolites and Nutraceuticals With Human Health Benefits. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 17 pp. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.740054>
- Górniak I., Bartoszewski R., and Króliczewski J. (2019).** Comprehensive review of antimicrobial activities of plant flavonoids. *Phytochemistry Reviews*18, 241–272. doi: 10.1007/s11101-018- 9591-z.
- Guevarra, B., Claustro, A., Madulid, R., Aguinaldo, A. Espeso, E. Nonato, M., Quinto, E., Santos M.A., De CastroBernas, G., Gonzales, R., Del Castillo Solevilla, R. and Ysrael, M. (2005).** A Guidebook to Plant Screening: Phytochemical and Biological (23-98).
- Gupta, S., Cox, S., Rajauria, G., Jaiswal, A. K., and Abu-Ghannam, N. (2012).** Growth inhibition of common food spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms in the presence of brown seaweed extracts. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, 5, 1907-1916.
- Henry, E. L., Redzwan, N. F. M., Badeges, N. F. A. K. and Surugau, S. (2022).** Characterization of biofilms developed from alginate extracted from *Padina* sp. incorporated with Calcium chloride (CaCl₂). *Journal of Physics*, 2314(1), 012022–012022. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2314/1/012022>
- Harsha-Mohan, E., Madhusudan, S., and Baskaran, R. (2023).** The sea lettuce *Ulva* sensu lato: Future food with health-promoting bioactives. *Algal Research*, 71, 103069–103069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2023.103069>
- Hudaifah, H., Mutamimah, D., and Utami, A. U. (2020).** Komponen Bioaktif dari *Eucheuma cottonii*, *Ulva lactuca*, *Halimeda opuntia*, dan *Padina australis*. *Jurnal LEMURU: Jurnal Ilmu Perikanan dan Kelautan Indonesia*, 2(2), 63–70. <https://doi.org/10.36526/lemuru.v2i2.1268>
- Ilyas, Z., Redha, A. A., Wu, Y. S., Ozeer, F. Z., and Aluko, R. E. (2023).** Nutritional and Health Benefits of the Brown Seaweed *Himantalia elongata*. *Plant Foods for Human Nutrition*, 78(2), 233–242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11130-023-01056-8>
- Johnson, A. B., Thompson, C. D., and Davis, E. F. (2017).** Antibacterial Properties of Tannins from Various Plant Sources. *Journal of Microbiology and Natural Products*, 8(2), 112-125.
- Julyasih, K. S. M and Purnawati, A. (2023).** Phytochemical Compounds and Antibacterial Activity to *Escherichia coli* of Green Macro Algae. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1131(1):012012, 5 pp. doi:10.1088/1755-1315/1131/1/012012
- Junopia, A. C., Hasnah, N., and Dali, S. (2020).** Effectiveness of Brown Algae (*Padina* spp.) Extract as Antioxidant Agent. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 1463: 012012, 5 pp. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1463/1/012012
- Kaczmarek, B. (2020).** Tannic Acid with Antiviral and Antibacterial Activity as A Promising Component of Biomaterials - A Mini review. *Materials (Basel, Switzerland)*, 13(14), 3224. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13143224>
- Kandhasamy, M. and Arunachalam, K. D. (2008).** Evaluation of in vitro antibacterial property of seaweeds of southeast coast of India. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 7(12): 1958- 1961.

- Khadijah, K., Soekamto, N. H., Firdaus, F., Chalid, S. M. T., and Syah, Y. M. (2021).** Chemical composition, phytochemical constituent, and toxicity of methanol extract of brown algae (*Padina* sp.) from Puntondo Coast, Takalar (Indonesia). *Journal of Food Quality and Hazards Control*. 8: 178-185.
- Khan, M. I., Ahhmed, A., Shin, J. H., Baek, J. S., Kim, M. Y., and Kim, J. D. (2018).** Green Tea Seed Isolated Saponins Exerts Antibacterial Effects against Various Strains of Gram Positive and Gram-Negative Bacteria, a Comprehensive Study In Vitro and In Vivo. *Hindawi*. 1-12 pp. doi.org/10.1155/2018/3486106
- Lakshmi, D. S., Sankaranarayanan, S., Gajaria, T. K., Li, G., Kujawski, W., Kujawa, J., and Navia, R. (2020).** A Short Review on the Valorization of Green Seaweeds and Ulvan: FEEDSTOCK for Chemicals and Biomaterials. *Biomolecules*, 10(7), 991. https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10070991
- Monteiro, M., Santos, R.A., Iglesias, P. et al.** Effect of extraction method and solvent system on the phenolic content and antioxidant activity of selected macro- and microalgae extracts. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 32, 349-362. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10811-019-01927-1
- Nawaz, H., Muhammad Aslam Shad, Rehman, N., Hina Andaleeb, & Ullah, N. (2020).** Effect of solvent polarity on extraction yield and antioxidant properties of phytochemicals from bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) seeds. *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 56. https://doi.org/10.1590/s2175-97902019000417129
- Nisha A, Pandima Devi K. (2014).** Assessment of mutagenic effect of *G. acerosa* and *S. wightii* in *S. typhimurium* (TA 98, TA 100, and TA 1538 strains) and evaluation of their cytotoxic and genotoxic effect in human mononuclear cells: a nonclinical study. *BioMed Research International*; 2014:1-8.
- Obidoa O., Joshua P.E, and Eze N. J. (2010).** Phytochemical Analysis of *Cocos nucifera* L. *Journal of Pharmacy Research* 3(2): 280-286
- Oumaskour, K., Boujaber, N., Etahiri, S., and Assobhei, O. (2012).** Screening of antibacterial and antifungal activities in green and brown algae from the coast of Sidi Bouzid (El Jadida, Morocco). *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 11(104), 16831-16837.
- Øverland, M., Mydland, L. T., and Skrede, A. (2018).** Marine macroalgae as sources of protein and bioactive compounds in feed for monogastric animals. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 99(1), 13-24. https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.9143
- Pepi, M. and Focardi, S. (2021).** Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria in Aquaculture and Climate Change: A Challenge for Health in the Mediterranean Area. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(11), 5723. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18115723
- Pérez, M. J., Falqué, E., and Domínguez, H. (2016).** Antimicrobial Action of Compounds from Marine Seaweed. *Marine drugs*, 14(3), 52. https://doi.org/10.3390/md14030052
- Pooja, S. (2014).** Algae used as Medicine and Food-A Short Review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research* 6(1), 33 - 35.
- Prasetyaningrum, A. Rokhati, N., Dharmawan, Y., and Prinanda, G. R. (2021).** Comparison study for extraction of bioactive flavonoids from *moringa oleifera*, apple, onion, and ascorbic acid (orange) by using microwave-assisted, ultrasound-assisted and maceration methods. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 1053(1), 012123- 012123. https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899x/1053/1/012123

- Pridgeon, J. W. and Klesius, P. H. (2013).** Pridgeon, J. W., & Klesius, P. H. (2012). Major bacterial diseases in aquaculture and their vaccine development. *CABI Reviews: Perspectives in Agriculture, Veterinary Science, Nutrition and Natural Resources*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1079/pavsnr20127048>
- Putra, N. R., Fajriah, S., Qomariyah, L., Dewi A. S., Rizkiyah, D. N., Irianto, I., Rusmin, D., Melati, M., Trisnawati, N. W., Darwati, I., and Arya, N. N. (2023).** Exploring the Potential of *Ulva lactuca*: Emerging Extraction Methods, Bioactive Compounds, and Health Applications - A Perspective Review. *South African Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 47, pp. 233- 245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajce.2023.11.017>
- Rachmawati, N. F., Nuryanti, I. F., and Adharani, N. (2021).** Phytochemicals and Antioxidant of Seaweed Tea *Padina australis*. *International Journal of Marine Engineering Innovation and Research*, 6(4), 255-258 <https://doi.org/10.12962/j25481479.v6i4.11636>
- Remya, R. R., Samrot, A. V., Kumar, S. S., Mohanavel, V., Karthick, A., Chinnaiyan, V. K., Umapathy, D., and Muhibbullah, M. (2022).** Bioactive Potential of Brown Algae. *Adsorption Science and Technology*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/9104835>
- Roh, H. J., Kim, A., Kang, G. S., and Kim, D. H. (2016).** Photoinactivation of major bacterial pathogens in aquaculture. *Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 19(28). 7 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41240-016-0029-5>
- Ruangpan, L. and Tendencia, E. A. (2004).** Laboratory manual of standardized methods for antimicrobial sensitivity test for bacteria isolated from aquaculture. Southeast Asian Fisheries Development Center, Aquaculture Department, Iloilo, Philippines.
- Saidin, S., Jumat, M. A., Amin, N. A. A., and Al-Hammadi, A. S. S. (2021).** Organic and inorganic antibacterial approaches in combating bacterial infection for biomedical application. *Materials Science and Engineering: C*, 118, 111382-111382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2020.111382>
- Shanmugam, J., Raman, K. D., Viswanathan, S., and Nallamuthu, T. (2013).** Antibacterial and antioxidant activity of red seaweeds from Kilakarai, Rameswaram, Tamil Nadu, India. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Sciences*, 32, 1386-1395.
- Singkoh, M. F. O., Katili, D. Y., Rumondor, and M. J. (2021).** Phytochemical screening and antibacterial activity of brown algae (*Padina australis*) from Atep Oki Coast, East Lembean of Minahasa Regency. *AAFL Bioflux* 14(1):455- 461.
- Sivagnanam, S. P., Yin, S., Choi, J. H., Park, Y. B., Woo, H. C., and Chun, B. S. (2015).** Biological Properties of Fucoxanthin in Oil Recovered from Two Brown Seaweeds Using Supercritical CO₂ Extraction. *Marine Drugs*. 2015; 13(6):3422-3442. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md13063422>
- Sobuj, M. K. A., Islam, M. A., Islam, M. S., Islam, M. M., Mahmud, Y., and Rafiquzzaman, S. M. (2021).** Effect of solvents on bioactive compounds and antioxidant activity of *Padina tetrastratica* and *Gracilaria tenuistipitata* seaweeds collected from Bangladesh. *Scientific reports*, 11(1), 19082. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-98461-3>
- Sofowora, A., Ogunbodede, E., and Onayade, A. (2013).** The role and place of medicinal plants in the strategies for disease prevention. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 10(5). <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajtcam.v10i5.2>

- Srikong, W., Bovornreungroj, N., Mittraparparthorn, P., and Bovornreungroj, P. (2017).** Antibacterial and antioxidant activities of differential solvent extractions from the green seaweed *Ulva intestinalis*. *ScienceAsia*, 43(2), 88-95.
- Tajrin, A., Chandha, M. H., Mappangara, S., Ruslin, M., Samad, R., and Akbar, F. H. (2020).** Analysis of the total level of flavonoids in the brown algae (Phaeophyceae) extract as analgesic and anti-inflammatory drugs. *Pesquisa Brasileira em Odontopediatria e Clínica Integrada*. 6 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1590/pboci.2020.103>
- Thanigaivel, S., Hindu Vidhya, S., Vijayakumar, S., Mukherjee, A., Chandrasekaran, N., and Thomas, J. (2015).** Differential solvent extraction of two seaweeds and their efficacy in controlling *Aeromonas salmonicida* infection in *Oreochromis mossambicus* a novel therapeutic approach. *Aquaculture*. 2015;433:56-64. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.03.010.
- Troell, M., Kautsky, N., Beveridge, M., Henriksson, P., Primavera, J., Rönnbäck, P., and Folke, C. (2013).** *Aquaculture*. Encyclopedia of Biodiversity, 189-201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-384719-5.00307-5>
- Trono, G. C. (1997).** Field Guide and atlas of the Seaweed Resources of the Philippines (Vol. 1). Bookmark Inc.
- Truong, D. H., Nguyen, D. H., Ta, N. A. T, Bui, A. V., Do, T. H., and Nguyen, H. C. (2019).** Evaluation of the Use of Different Solvents for Phytochemical Constituents, Antioxidants, and In Vitro Anti-Inflammatory Activities of *Severinia buxifolia*. *Journal of Food Quality*, 2019, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/8178294>
- Vatsos, I. N. and Rebours, C. (2015).** Seaweed extracts as antimicrobial agents in aquaculture. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 27, 2017-2035.
- Vieira, E. F., Soares, C., Machado, S., Correia, M., Ramalhosa, M. J., OlivaTeles, M. T., Carvalho, A. P., Domingues, V. F., Antunes, F., Oliveira, T. A. C., Morais, S., and Delerue-Matos, C. (2018).** Seaweeds from the Portuguese coast as a source of proteinaceous material: Total and free amino acid composition profile. *Food Chem.* 269:264-275. [10.1016/j.foodchem.2018.06.145](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2018.06.145)
- Wichard, T., Charrier, B., Frédéric Mineur, Bothwell, J. H., De Clerck, O, and Coates, J. C. (2015).** The green seaweed *Ulva*: a model system to study morphogenesis. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2015.00072>
- Xie, Y., Yang, W., Tang, F., Chen, X., & Ren, L. (2015).** Antibacterial activities of flavonoids: structure-activity relationship and mechanism. *Current medicinal chemistry*, 22(1), 132-149. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867321666140916113443>
- Yilmaz, N. K. and Schiffer, C. A. (2021)** Introduction: Drug Resistance. *ACS Publication Chemical Reviews* 121(6), 3235-3237. doi: 10.1021/acs.chemrev.1c00118
- Zhang, L., Zhang, S., Gong-fu, Y. E., and Qin, X. (2019).** Seasonal variation and ecological importance of tannin and nutrient concentrations in *Casuarina equisetifolia* branchlets and fine roots. *Journal of Forestry Research*, 31(5), 1499-1508. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11676-019-00991-0>

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